

**EDUCATING CHILDREN IN THE SPIRIT OF NATIONAL
VALUES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS
AND IN THE FAMILY.**

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Abstract: Raising children based on national values in pre-school educational organizations and in the family is one of today's urgent issues. Teaching children in the family and in pre-school educational organizations through national traditions, children's interest in national values serves to raise the morale of our children.

Аннотация: Воспитание детей в духе национальных ценностей в дошкольных образовательных организациях и в семье. На основе сотрудничества семейного и дошкольного образования разработаны методические пояснения по воспитанию детей через национальные традиции, интерес детей к национальным ценностям.

Children's education has become important in every era. Even today, this issue is an urgent problem. We can imagine the future of our country depending on the knowledge of the growing young generation and what kind of people they will be in the future. That's why they say: "The future is in the hands of young people." Raising a child starts the family. We call the family "small homeland". This Motherland will be the primary education school for the child. In a sense, parents are the first teachers of their children. Therefore, parents should have high moral qualities. The child of a parent who can set an example for a child with good qualities will be a well-rounded person with good character, high knowledge, and a benefit to the nation in the future.

Educating young people is a sacred duty of every parent to the Motherland. He should approach this duty responsibly. "Parents who want to secure their future should spend their time and effort on raising their children, who will be great people of tomorrow. The work spent on other areas may be wasted, but the work spent on the development of the child will become an inexhaustible treasure. It is no exaggeration to say that the money and time spent on the development of a child will be the basis for a prosperous life tomorrow. Preparing children of preschool age for school education is an important aspect of increasing the effectiveness of teaching. Preparation for studying at school is an important result of preschool education organization and education given to children in the family. It is determined by the set of requirements that the school sets for the child. The unique aspect of these requirements embodies the new socio-psychological position of the student, the new tasks and duties that he must perform.

By psychologically and pedagogically preparing the children of the preschool preparation group for school education, children's adaptation to the school environment is much easier. Through the natural adaptation of children to school conditions, it is possible to achieve educational efficiency from the first period of the school period.

The following factors are important in the general preparation of children for school education:

- Moral and spiritual readiness of the child to study at school;
- Mental readiness of the child to study at school;
- Physical readiness of a preschool child to study at school.

The moral and moral preparation of the child to study at school prepares the ground for the child's adaptation to school conditions, responsible fulfillment of his obligations, and the formation of his moral attitude towards teachers and students. Spiritual and moral preparation is inextricably linked with mental and physical preparation of my child. The preschool education organization's system

of working with the family should have a clear goal and content. In terms of cooperation with parents, it is necessary to first analyze the results of achievements and experiences, show the positive sides of the child, and then gradually eliminate the negative situations in their behavior, and make an effort to increase their interest in the environment. So, what should be the preparation of a child of preschool age? an important question arises.

In order to ensure the comprehensive development of the child, the work of the preschool education organization in cooperation with parents is also considered important.

In this:

1. taking into account the opinions of parents regarding the organization of preschool education;
2. educating parents on issues of early development;
3. involving parents to actively participate in the educational process;
4. support for parents' initiatives to participate in the life of the organization.

Abu Ali ibn Sina wrote in his book "The Laws of Medicine": "The teacher's focus is on improving the child's character, on making the child's strong anger, fear, harsh nature alien to him, on what the child wants and strives for. and it is necessary to focus on not doing what he does not like in front of him. With this, two-sided benefits are achieved: firstly, a strong positive character is formed in the child from his early childhood; secondly, such development has a positive effect on the physical development of the child. After all, anger is a powerful motivator, a heavy nature is exhausting, and laziness reduces vital forces."

From time immemorial, our forefathers attached great importance to the young generation growing up to be well-behaved, polite, knowledgeable, capable children. If a child grows up to be incompetent, not only the parents will suffer, but also the country, society, and state. That is why family education has important political significance. A child with a strong imagination receives his

first upbringing in the family. "It is necessary to start education from the day of birth, to strengthen our body, to clarify our mind"

It is not for nothing that there are many myths, legends, proverbs and tales about raising a child among our people. Wise people say that a child should be educated from the mother's womb. When a child is well-educated, he can become a perfect scholar and a perfect person.

In conclusion, parents are role models for children and ideal people for them. Children take their parents' views as an example. Even according to scientific evidence, when a child is growing up in the mother's womb, what kind of emotion does the mother have (sadness, happiness, crying, hating a person), this is also transmitted from mother to child during pregnancy. as long as Therefore, it is necessary to start helping the mother to raise her child during pregnancy. It is important for parents to give their children basic education and upbringing at home in addition to the school environment, to open the way for them to discover a new world. for the child's development, both the teacher and the parents, and even the child himself, must make an effort. Only then will there be growth and results. The role of parents in raising a child is incomparable. Parents should pay attention to their child's upbringing and learning. In order for society to progress, education must be effective. For effective upbringing, parents should be knowledgeable. Our children will develop the country with knowledge.

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